

RESEARCH PROJECT OUTLINE

E-CURATORS - Pervasive Digital Curation Activities, Objects and Infrastructures in Archaeological Research and Communication: Process Modeling, Multiple-Case Studies, and Requirements Elicitation

1. Background and motivation

The curation of archaeological collections – artefacts, excavation records, photographs, laboratory notes and, increasingly, digital data emerging from archaeological research – is recognized as an important part of the work of archaeologists, regulated by established criteria, conditions, methods and procedures ensuring adequate archaeological curation “from the field to the repository” (Drewett, 2011, pp. 126–144; Ferguson & Murray, 1997; Johnson, 2003; Limp, 2005; Sullivan & Childs, 2003). Yet since the 1980s a global curation crisis has been identified in archaeology (Bawaya, 2007; Bustard, 2000; Childs, 1995), linked with the proliferation of partially recorded, disorganized, and endangered archaeological collections and documentation archives, including those from commercial archaeology, and with the lack of effective and cost-efficient policies and mechanisms to ensure the long-term preservation and future usability of archaeological research archives. This curation crisis takes a new impetus today, with increased risks for the archaeological record associated with armed conflict, environmental hazards, or limited resources.

Archaeology was one of the first disciplines to adopt digital tools and methods among the human sciences as early as the mid-1950s (Cowgill, 1967; Dallas, 2016b; Huggett, 2013), and remains an early adopter of cutting-edge digital technologies, e.g. (Earl et al., 2014; Giligny, Djindjan, Costa, Moscati, & Robert, 2015). However, using digital technologies as a means of ensuring long-term preservation and future reuse of archaeological resources only became relevant within broader developments on research data management and preservation. Specifically, the emergence of digital curation as an approach to professional work in information management, archival science (Ross, 2007) or library and information science (Palmer, Renear, & Cragin, 2008), aimed at “maintaining, preserving and adding value to digital research data throughout its lifecycle” (DCC, 2014), led in the last decade to the advancement of solutions ensuring the long-term preservation of authentic and reliable research information objects for future use under professional stewardship. This approach has been based on the adoption of “trusted repositories”, preservation metadata and interoperability standards, cost models, certification and risk management procedures (Dallas, 2007; Lee & Tibbo, 2007).

While valuable in the case of information resources under custodial control, it has been claimed that this approach to digital curation is increasingly incapable to address the diversity and messiness of pervasive curation practices in the contemporary digital environment (Constantopoulos & Dallas, 2008). In fact, apart from information professionals and archivists, the praxis of digital curation today involves a wide spectrum of communities, including amateur citizens, researchers, educators and creatives. Production of meaning becomes inextricably reliant on the curation of digital objects, as these are appraised and

selected, described and documented, annotated, enriched, and placed in the context of linked structures and narratives (Dallas, 2007). These digital objects are increasingly produced and used with off-the-shelf digital tools, within personal information devices and networked infrastructures (Dallas, 2016a). Fuelled by digital communities and social media networks (Blanchard & Horan, 1998; Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010; O'Reilly, 2007; Rheingold, 1993), the ubiquity of digital photo, video and audio recording devices (Van House & Churchill, 2008) and the rise of life-logging (Gemmell, Bell, & Lueder, 2006; Whittaker et al., 2012), crowdsourcing and user-generated content (Howe, 2006; Oomen & Aroyo, 2011; van Dijck, 2009), pro-am digitization (Terras, 2010) and the "citizen archivist" (Cox, 2009), pervasive digital curation practices privilege curation "at the source", enrichment and continuous evolution of information resources, and "pluralizing" of cultural meanings (McKemmish, 2001).

Emerging digital practices or archaeological research and communication resonate with these trends. The influential call towards open archaeology fuels new modes of content production through approaches such as mash-ups and microblogging (Lake, 2012, p. 471), reconfiguring the production of archaeological knowledge (Huggett, 2015). It is, also, tied to a rising call for the democratization and inclusive access to archaeological information. Public or community archaeology, foregrounding the importance of involving local knowledge and amateurs in the investigation and interpretation of the past (Moser et al., 2002), is increasingly supported by practices of engagement with digital archaeological resources, open models, digital fabrication, and interaction on social media networks (Beale, 2012; Beale & Beale, 2012; Morgan & Eve, 2012; Moser et al., 2002; Perry & Beale, 2015; Richardson, 2013). Virtual archaeology (Reilly, 1990), based on curated virtual reality 3D models suitable for theory construction (Gillings, 2005), is given new life as "additive archaeology" (Reilly & Beale, 2014): hybrid, material-digital curation in the guise of 3D printing of virtual archaeological realities. On the other hand, archaeological projects increasingly communicate data, fieldwork news and reports, and initiate dialogue, peer review and data reuse via Web 2.0 technologies (Isto Huvila, 2014; Kansa, Kansa, & Watrall, 2011; Perry & Beale, 2015). To simplify the creation, curation and publication of archaeological information, they also adopt Web-based solutions intended for cultural heritage collections such as Omeka (Kucsmas, Reiss, & Sidman, 2010), for capturing indigenous knowledge and accounting for cultural protocols such as Mukurtu (Wiberg, 2014), or specifically for archaeology such as Open Context (Kansa, 2010). Such digital curation practices appear often in project presentations and critical assessments of tools and approaches in recent proceedings of specialized conferences such as Computer Applications in Archaeology (CAA) (Earl et al., 2014; Giligny et al., 2015). Yet despite growing scholarly interest, pervasive digital curation practices in archaeology and their epistemic and cultural implications remain underexplored and poorly understood. The E-CURATORS project aims to address this gap.

2. Scope, objectives and research questions

Archaeologists increasingly use widely available, off-the-shelf tools to construct and curate digital photos, diaries, annotations, reflexive video recording, 3D models and GIS representations, databases, blogs and online reports. Digital archaeological objects today often are to be found outside custodially controlled collections and circulate "in the wild" through social media networks and cloud infrastructures. These novel, pervasive practices of archaeological digital curation affect not only how scholarly knowledge and evidence is produced, but also how diverse non-professional communities experience and reclaim the archaeological record in contexts of storytelling, contestation and cultural appropriation. The E-CURATORS project funded by an SSHRC Insight grant, seeks to advance scholarly knowledge on these developments, viewed from the viewpoint of digital curation: the process of maintaining, preserving and

adding value to digital objects (DCC, 2014) within the increasingly mainstreamed, pervasive, and invisible digital infrastructures that condition archaeological curation practices today (Dallas, 2016a), involving not only archaeological research and communication, but also cultural memory, social representation and symbolic appropriation, arising in the context of nationalist, post-colonial and indigenous archaeologies (Habu, Fawcett, & Matsunaga, 2008; Hamilakis, 2008; Kohl, 1998; Meskell, 1998; Trigger, 1984).

Our study looks, in particular, into pervasive curation practices, manifested in archaeological research and communication work in the digital continuum, or “in the wild”, i.e. .e. outside custodial collections or professional stewardship (Dallas, 2016a). We look at phenomena such as: adoption of mobile devices to capture and document archaeological evidence in excavation and survey; use of off-the-shelf mobile apps to construct three-dimensional models of archaeological artefacts, or to geo-locate archaeological information resources; instant online aggregation of captured data and resources in research archives, databases and repositories at the time of capture; use of synchronous and asynchronous communication technologies to connect researchers with data and enable interpretation “at the trowel’s edge” (Hodder, 1997); collaborative annotation, enrichment and interpretation of archaeological data using Web 2.0 technologies, crowdsourcing and social tagging; adoption of virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) visualization methods and equipment used in other fields (such as the media and gaming industries) for the generation and assessment of archaeological hypotheses, interpretation and communication; use of blogs, wikis and social media networks to co-create and co-curate archaeological information objects; open access provision of data outside established archaeological data infrastructures; and, the use of gamification, storytelling and social media networks for public communication, learning and mediation.

E-CURATORS has the following objectives: (a) to produce a formal conceptual model and an evidence-based account of pervasive practices of digital curation in archaeological research and communication; (b) to identify and assess their implication on issues of epistemic and pragmatic importance for the future of the digital archaeological record; and, (c) to elicit requirements for digital infrastructures, as well as methods, procedures and best practice recommendations capable of addressing these issues. To support these objectives, the study poses the following research questions:

- (a) What are the most important kinds of pervasive digital curation activity in emerging archaeological practice, and what is their compositional structure, actors, goals, procedures, methods and mediating tools?
- (b) What kinds of digital information objects are involved in pervasive archaeological digital curation practice, what are their significant properties and how are they manifested in data representation schemes, metadata and paradata?
- (c) What are the implications of these practices on questions of integrity and authenticity, reliability, longevity, and functionality of digital archaeological objects for future scholarly work, education, communication and community engagement?
- (d) What kinds of systems, methods, procedures and practices could be adopted by actors (researchers, museum curators, amateur archaeologists, archivists, data managers, etc.) to ensure the integrity and authenticity, longevity, reliability and functionality of digital archaeological objects?
- (e) What is the impact of pervasive digital curation infrastructures, processes and methods on questions of cultural appropriation and contestation involving researchers, professional archaeologists,

amateurs, and local, indigenous and descendant communities, and which values, principles and procedures can be adopted to ensure ethical, inclusive and reciprocal practice?

3. Data and methods

E-CURATORS is a mixed-methods, multiple-case study of archaeological projects employing novel digital technologies of curation “in the wild”. The units of inquiry are a number of case studies/archaeological activity sites, ranging from survey and excavation to digital illustration, long term digital preservation and access, and public communication and participatory curation of archaeological heritage. The focus is on archaeological practice and knowledge work by individuals who are core members of included projects, covering different phases of the digital curation lifecycle, on account of their potential to reveal regularities, but also complementary phenomena and diversity in pervasive practice across cases. An initial corpus of cases to be included in E-CURATORS has been selected through a purposive approach, evaluating their capacity to provide useful evidence and insight on novel practices of digital curation “in the wild” and limiting the scope to projects from North America and Europe. Additional or alternative cases may be sought, to ensure saturation with regard to research questions, and adequate confirmation of findings through triangulation.

For each case study, E-CURATORS will collect, keep, organize and analyze the following kinds of research data:

- (a) Testimonies and stories related by study subjects-members of each archaeological project/case study site, individually or in conversation, acquired through a combination of life history and semi-open episodic interviewing approach. Historical (factual), attitudinal and normative dimensions of activity pertaining to the digital curation of archaeology-related assets will be the focus of qualitative interviewing. Given the diversity and emergent nature of practices in focus of E-CURATORS and their potential implications for digital curation, questions will vary and conversation will be allowed to develop organically, with the interviewees being “in the driving seat”. “Why” and “how” questions will emerge directly from information volunteered by interviewees and will focus on eliciting speech acts on the nested structure of archaeological curation activity, its historical biography and “significant events”, the actants and “significant others” involved in it, their motives and goals, the significant properties of information objects created, curated and used, and their archaeological and cultural referents.
- (b) Naturalistic observation of study subjects as they engage strictly in activities related to the archaeological project/case study, especially as regards the use of pervasive digital technologies and the curation of archaeological information assets, either onsite or offsite, either alone or in interaction with other study subjects.
- (c) Documentary evidence related to the activity of study subjects in the archaeological project/case study, including evidence on the archaeological context and referents to their activity (e.g., an excavation trench, feature or find), captured field data, digital photos, 3D models, notes, audio recordings, video recordings, sketches and doodles, logbook entries, context sheet recording forms, captions, database entries, statistical and data summarizations, presentations, GIS maps, cataloguing texts, written and digital-online communications, reports, blogs, posts, tweets, website content, visual illustrations, published research articles, monographs, etc.
- (d) Digital recordings, in the form of video, audio, photography, screen capture, digital file copies, researcher notes, or any other relevant means of capture and representation of testimonies and

stories, naturalistic observations, and documentary evidence identified above, collected from the case study sites, suitably transcribed, coded, annotated and transformed to a format amenable to qualitative data analysis, search and retrieval, visualization, summarization, and use for substantive interpretation and theory building by the E-CURATORS research team.

Following a cultural-historical activity theory (CHAT) approach (Allen, Karanasios, & Slavova, 2011; Dallas, 2007; Engeström, 2000; Kaptelinin & Nardi, 2007; Leont'ev, 1978) and its application in the interdisciplinary field of digital curation (Harvey, 2010; Higgins, 2011; Yakel, 2007), data will be transcribed, "coded" and annotated using the MAXQDA qualitative data analysis software. Organization, coding and thematic analysis of transcribed data within MAXQDA will adhere to an extensible "coding system", derived from a conceptual model of archaeological digital curation activity based on a synthesis between relevant entities and relations of the NeDiMAH Methods Ontology (Hughes, Constantopoulos, & Dallas, 2016; Pertsas & Constantopoulos, 2016), the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model and relevant CIDOC CRM extensions (Crofts, Doerr, Gill, Stead, & Stiff, 2004; Strubulis, Flouris, Tzitzikas, & Doerr, 2014) and set of taxonomies (hierarchical lists of classification terms). The conceptual model, and derived MAXQDA data structure and coding system, will represent evidence on (a) activities, actors, their goals and motives, archaeological entities, information resources, methods, procedures, digital devices, tools and services encountered in the case studies, and (b) problems/issues, positions/solutions/ideas, and criteria/considerations/arguments elicited from study subjects on "how" and "why" they understand, decide and act in their archaeological practice. MAXQDA data will be encoded to support semi-automatic mapping to labeled graph data within a Neo4J database, allowing associative navigation, filtering, query, summarization and extraction of synthetic views of the evidence collected from case studies, to: a) identify recurrent digital curation activity types underlying the practices observed, traced in documents, and accounted for by interviewees in the multiple-case studies; b) account for the compositional structure of particular activity types (e.g., how digital annotation on an archaeological feature in a Digital Elevation Model of a trench fits with checking accuracy in the way the feature is represented, within a broader activity of curating the Model); c) account for the interdependence between processes, objects and human agency; study the interaction between external aspects of activity, visible through observation of actions, physical and digital traces and documents, etc., and internal aspects, related to the motives, goals, norms and symbolic capital of human actors; d) identify how pervasive digital infrastructures, digital objects, as well as norms, methods and routinized processes act as "mediating tools" for digital curation.

To identify an initial framework for interpretation, E-CURATORS draws from "sensitizing concepts" such as epistemic cultures (Knorr-Cetina, 1999), objectual practice (Knorr-Cetina, 2001), delegation (Latour, 1992, 2009), infrastructural inversion (Bowker, 1994), distributed cognition in the wild (Hutchins, 2006), object biography (Gosden & Marshall, 1999; Hoskins, 2006), efficacious objects and distributed personhood (Gell, 1998). Drawing from social studies of practice (Bourdieu, 1977; Knorr-Cetina, 1999; Lynch, 1997; Savolainen, 2007; Schatzki, Knorr-Cetina, & von Savigny, 2001), recordkeeping continuum theory (McKemmish, 2001; Upward, McKemmish, & Reed, 2011), as well as from pragmatist (James, 1907; Peirce, 1878; Putnam, 1995) and critical realist (Archer, 1998; Bhaskar, 1989; Mingers, 2004) epistemological traditions, we will synthesize and extend earlier ethnographic (Edgeworth, 2006), social studies of practice (Hutchins, 2006; Goodwin, 2010) epistemological (Chapman & Wylie, 2014; Gardin, 1980; Wylie, 2002) and information studies (Huvila, 2008) investigations of archaeological work.

4. Originality, expected contribution and impact

E-CURATORS is based on wide-ranging investigation of multiple-case studies from different national contexts and scholarly traditions, whose scope ranges from automated archaeological data capture in the field to social interaction between archaeologists and diverse designated communities. The project focuses on novel digital practices. It is based on a holistic investigation of pervasive digital infrastructures, tools and services used not only by professional researchers but also by amateurs, source communities and other archaeological stakeholders. It is, also, the first study on archaeological information work, and one of the first generally, to propose and apply a formal domain model (based on the NeDIMAH Methods Ontology, NeMO) for the representation of empirical evidence collected through qualitative interviewing, naturalistic inquiry and document analysis of multiple-case studies.

The motivation for the study is our conviction that archaeology needs urgently to come to terms with the social, ethical and political implications of its practice. This hinges especially on the way it produces particular versions of the archaeological record through invisibly accepted methods of recording, documentation, analysis and presentation, which change significantly with the advent of pervasive infrastructures such as global networks, mobile recording devices, off-the-shelf applications and Application Programming Interfaces. As archaeological resources become the focus of community interaction and contestation, and as paradigms of open and community archaeology establish themselves in archaeological praxis, an evidence-based, wide-ranging in terms of scope, and theoretically rigorous inquiry on the structure of curation activities operating on digital archaeological objects in the continuum will yield significant knowledge on the articulation between information processes and archaeological meaning making.

By investigating a mix of paradigmatic digital archaeology projects from North America and Europe, the E-CURATORS project will address a significant knowledge gap on emerging digital practices in archaeology, and on emerging archaeological practices in the digital domain at large. It will provide a coherently theorized, extensively substantiated and rigorously defined account of pervasive archaeological digital curation practices, and of the diverse actors, information objects, digital tools, procedures and methods involved in them, and on this basis establish suitable practical requirements for digital objects representation, systems and procedures and recommendations for best practice on digital infrastructures, methods and procedures for archaeological digital curation. We will also contribute to digital curation theory, especially with regard to the formal conceptualization of pervasive curation activity, and the formal conceptual representation of the archaeological record and digital information objects; again, this contribution is not merely a theoretical gesture, but has salient implications on the pragmatic, ethical and political entailments of pervasive digital curation practices in archaeology with regard to questions of authenticity, reliability, reciprocity and appropriation, and their implications for the identification of values and principles that should govern the operation of systems and procedures supporting the digital curation of archaeological assets “in the wild”. By elaborating a formal ontological model of digital curation activity, and by developing a multiple-case study protocol suitable for the representation of widely diverse curation practices in archaeological research and community engagement, we will also contribute to the formal theorization of meaning-making practices in the study of epistemic cultures, archaeological heritage interpretation, and social media communication. On account of its topic and approach, our study will hopefully contribute to disciplines and research communities beyond information studies, including digital preservation and curation, archival science, social studies of science, practice

studies, digital media studies, material culture studies, cultural heritage management, and museum studies.

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